

On the Viscosity of Liquids and the Dependence of the Viscosity Constants on Constitutional Factors.

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Porter (*Phil. Mag.*, 1912, **23**, 458) showed that the logarithm of the mobility (inverse of viscosity) of a liquid plotted against the logarithm of its vapour pressure at the same temperature gave a straight line. In other words,

$$\text{Log } \eta = m \log p + C_1 \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

where η represents viscosity, p vapour pressure and m and C_1 two constants. From the integration of the Clausius-Clapeyron equation connecting Q (heat of evaporation), p (vapour pressure) and T (absolute temperature), it follows that

$$\log p = -\frac{Q}{RT} + C_2 \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

By combining equations (1) and (2) we get

$$\log \eta = a + \frac{\beta}{T} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

where a and β are constants, an equation given in the form $\frac{1}{\eta} = Ae^{-\frac{Q}{RT}}$

by Dunn (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1926, **22**, 401), in the form $\eta = Ae^{\frac{b}{T}}$

by Andrade (*Nature*, 1930, **125**, 309) and in the form $\log \phi = -\frac{k}{T} + C$

where $\phi = \frac{1}{\eta}$ by Sheppard (*Nature*, 1930, **125**, 489). Porter (*loc. cit.*) suggested

$$F(M) = f(\mu) = A + \frac{B}{T},$$

where μ represents viscosity and M mobility ($\frac{1}{\mu}$). It is surprising that Porter did not suggest that $f(\mu) = \log \mu$.

The relationship which Porter finds between T/T_0 and T where T and T_0 are the temperatures of the two liquids at which their viscosities are the same, can really be derived for unassociated liquids from $\log \eta = a + \frac{\beta}{T}$. By combining two such equations, it can be shown that

$$\frac{T}{T_0} = \frac{a - \bar{a}_0}{\beta_0} \cdot T + \frac{\beta}{\beta_0}.$$

In other words T/T_0 plotted against T will give a straight line as found by Porter (*loc. cit.*)

It is difficult to understand why T/T_0 plotted against T should give a straight line in the cases where one or both of the liquids are associated. The formula which Andrade (*Nature*, 1930, **125**, 582) suggests for the associated liquids has the form

$$\log \eta_0 = \bar{a}_0 + \frac{\beta_0}{T_0 - \theta}.$$

If we combine this equation with $\log \eta = \bar{a} + \frac{\beta}{T}$, the equation representing the viscosity of unassociated liquids, we get

$$\frac{T_0 - \theta}{T} = m (T_0 - \theta) + k \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{T_1}{T_0 - \theta} = m' T + k' \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

So if Andrade's formulæ be correct, T/T_0 plotted against T should not give a straight line if one or both of the liquids are associated. Actually it does, as shown by Porter in case of mercury and the water (*loc. cit.*). Andrade (*loc. cit.*) also considers this to be an unfailing rule. Some more substances are being examined by the author to test the correctness or otherwise of this relationship.

The object of the present paper is two-fold: first to test the formula for non-associated liquids and secondly to see the extent to

which the constants α and β depend on the constitution of the compounds. The following liquids have been examined: pentane, isopentane, hexane, isohexane, heptane, isoheptane, octane, methyl iodide, ethyl iodide, propyl iodide, isopropyl iodide, butyl iodide, isobutyl iodide, allyl chloride, allyl bromide, allyl iodide, ethyl bromide, isopropyl chloride, isopropyl bromide, propyl chloride, propyl bromide, isobutyl chloride, isobutyl bromide, mono-chloro-benzene, and mono-bromo-benzene.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Experimental Test of the Formulæ for the Viscosity of Unassociated Liquids.

In the following Tables α , β , η (observed), η (calculated) and the % difference between the calculated and observed results for the various liquids are given.

<i>n-Pentane.</i>				<i>i.oPentane.</i>			
$\alpha = 4.2600.$ $\beta = 328.$				$\alpha = \bar{4}.2104.$ $\beta = 339.$			
$t^\circ.$	$\eta(o) \times 10^6.$	$\eta(c) \times 10^6.$	% Diff.	$t^\circ.$	$\eta(o) \times 10^6.$	$\eta(c) \times 10^6.$	% Diff.
0	2894	2893	0.0	0	2833	2833	0.0
10	2624	2624	0.0	10	2564	2563	0.0
20	2395	2395	0.0	20	2331	2330	0.0
30	2200	2200	0.0				

<i>n-Hexane.</i>				<i>isoHexane.</i>			
$\alpha = 4.2495.$ $\beta = 370.$				$\alpha = \bar{4}.2358.$ $\beta = 366.$			
$t^\circ.$	$\eta(o) \times 10^6.$	$\eta(c) \times 10^6.$	% Diff.	$t^\circ.$	$\eta(o) \times 10^6.$	$\eta(c) \times 10^6.$	% Diff.
0	4020	4025	0.1	0	3760	3771	0.3
10	3602	3605	0.1	10	3381	3381	0.0
20	3258	3253	0.2	20	3061	3054	0.2
30	2963	2955	0.3	30	2791	2778	0.0
40	2708	2701	0.3	40	2541	2542	0.0
50	2483	2482	0.0	50	2331	2339	0.3
60	2288	2294	0.3	60	2161	2162	0.0

Heptane.

$$\alpha = \bar{4} \cdot 2336. \quad \beta = 406.$$

t° .	$\eta(o) \times 10^6$.	$\eta(c) \times 10^6$.	% Diff.	t° .	$\eta(o) \times 10^6$.	$\eta(c) \times 10^6$.	% Diff.
0	5236	5249	0.2	50	3105	3095	0.3
10	4653	4658	0.2	60	2841	2837	0.1
20	4163	4162	0.0	70	2617	2614	0.1
30	3754	3746	0.2	80	2413	2420	0.3
40	3410	3395	0.4	90	2239	2250	0.5

*isoHeptane.**Octane.*

$$\alpha = \bar{4} \cdot 2316.$$

$$\beta = 396.$$

$$\alpha = \bar{4} \cdot 1790.$$

$$\beta = 456.$$

t° .	$\eta(o) \times 10^6$.	$\eta(c) \times 10^6$.	% Diff.	t° .	$\eta(o) \times 10^6$.	$\eta(c) \times 10^6$.	% Diff.
0	4811	4811	0.0	0	7060	7068	0.1
10	4278	4268	0.2	10	6159	6169	0.1
20	3842	3830	0.3	20	4828	4830	0.3
30	3472	3456	0.5	30	4828	4830	0.0
40	3152	3139	0.4	40	4328	4324	0.1
50	2881	2668	0.4	50	3907	3897	0.3
60	2642	2635	0.3	60	3551	3535	0.5
70	2426	2433	0.3	70	3241	3224	0.5
80	2242	2254	0.5	80	2971	2957	0.5
90	2087	2101	0.7	90	2730	2724	0.2
				100	2520	2521	0.0
				110	2335	2342	0.3
				120	2160	2184	1.1

*Propyl chloride.**isoPropyl chloride.*

$$\alpha = \bar{4} \cdot 3190.$$

$$\beta = 362.$$

$$\alpha = \bar{4} \cdot 2480.$$

$$\beta = 372.$$

t° .	$\eta(o) \times 10^6$.	$\eta(c) \times 10^6$.	% Diff.	t° .	$\eta(o) \times 10^6$.	$\eta(c) \times 10^6$.	% Diff.
0	4416	4416	0.0	0	4080	4080	0.0
10	3963	3963	0.0	10	3646	3652	0.2
20	3589	3583	0.2	20	3292	3294	0.1
30	3264	3264	0.0	30	2993	2990	0.1
40	2990	2989	0.0				

isoButyl chloride.

Allyl chloride.

$\alpha = \bar{4} \cdot 2203.$

$\beta = \bar{4}23.$

$\alpha = \bar{4} \cdot 3299.$

$\beta = \bar{3}51.$

t°	$\eta(0) \times 10^6$	$\eta(c) \times 10^6$	% Diff.	t°	$\eta(0) \times 10^6$	$\eta(c) \times 10^6$	% Diff.
0	5878	5884	0.1	0	4127	4127	0.0
10	5188	5188	0.0	10	3718	3717	0.0
20	4617	4612	0.1	20	3374	3372	0.1
30	4138	4134	0.1	30	3074	3076	0.1
40	3729	3731	0.1	40	2825	2827	0.1
50	3389	3388	0.0				
60	3090	3091	0.0				

Chlorobenzene.

Bromobenzene.

$\alpha = \bar{4} \cdot 3278.$

$\beta = \bar{4}68.$

$\alpha = \bar{4} \cdot 4240.$

$\beta = \bar{4}88.$

t°	$\eta(0) \times 10.6$	$\eta(c) \times 10.6$	% Diff	t°	$\eta(0) \times 10.6$	$\eta(c) \times 10.6$	% Diff.
10	9582	9582	0.0	10	14076	14076	0.0
15	8969	8969	0.0	15	13173	13135	0.4
20	8391	8416	0.3	20	12271	12289	0.1
25	7904	7912	0.1	25	11369	11525	1.5
30	7435	7452	0.2	30	10647	10825	1.7
40	6659	6637	0.3	40	9564	9619	0.8
50	5991	5981	0.2	50	8662	8609	0.6

Ethyl bromide.

Propyl bromide.

$\alpha = \bar{4} \cdot 4601.$

$\beta = \bar{3}35.$

$\alpha = \bar{4} \cdot 4216.$

$\beta = \bar{3}80.$

t°	$\eta(0) \times 10.6$	$\eta(c) \times 10.6$	% Diff.	t°	$\eta(0) \times 10.6$	$\eta(c) \times 10.6$	% Diff.
0	4866	4869	0.1	0	6509	6509	0.0
10	4407	4406	0.0	10	5815	5813	0.0
20	4020	4015	0.1	20	5241	5230	0.2
30	3678	3681	0.1	30	4748	4745	0.1
				40	4338	4322	0.4
				50	3966	3964	0.1
				60	3563	3653	0.0
				70	3374	3385	0.2

Allyl bromide.

$$\alpha = \bar{4} \cdot 4310. \quad \beta = 373.$$

t° .	$\eta(o) \times 10^6$	$\eta(c) \times 10^6$	% Diff.
0	6258	6241	0.3
10	5595	5597	0.0
20	5097	5047	0.2
30	4581	4581	0.0
40	4192	4184	0.2
50	3844	3844	0.0
60	3545	3551	0.2
70	3279	3292	0.4

isoPropyl bromide.

$$\alpha = \bar{4} \cdot 3582. \quad \beta = 390.$$

t° .	$\eta(o) \times 10^6$	$\eta(c) \times 10^6$	% Diff.
0	6106	6119	0.2
10	5448	5447	0.0
20	4894	4889	0.1
30	4431	4419	0.4
40	4028	4019	0.2
50	3680	3680	0.0

isoButyl bromide.

$$\alpha = \bar{4} \cdot 3062. \quad \beta = 440.$$

t° .	$\eta(o) \times 10^6$.	$\eta(c) \times 10^6$.	% Diff.	t° .	$\eta(o) \times 10^6$.	$\eta(c) \times 10^6$.	% Diff.
0	8277	8277	0.0	50	4695	4659	0.8
10	7257	7261	0.1	60	4265	4241	0.6
20	6433	6424	0.1	70	3902	3882	0.3
30	5749	5737	0.2	80	3573	3570	0.1
40	5179	5156	0.4	90	3260	3299	1.2

Methyl iodide.

$$\alpha = \bar{4} \cdot 5728. \quad \beta = 330.$$

t° .	$\eta(o) \times 10^6$.	$\eta(c) \times 10^6$.	% Diff.
0	6055	6049	0.1
10	5481	5481	0.0
20	5001	5001	0.0
30	4601	4591	0.2
40	4240	4255	0.4

Ethyl iodide.

$$\alpha = \bar{4} \cdot 5501. \quad \beta = 358.$$

t° .	$\eta(o) \times 10^6$.	$\eta(c) \times 10^6$.	% Diff.
0	7269	7269	0.0
10	6537	6533	0.1
20	5925	5916	0.2
30	5403	5391	0.2
40	4951	4955	0.1
50	4558	4555	0.1
60	4217	4219	0.0
70	3914	3925	0.3

Propyl iodide.

$\alpha = \bar{4} \cdot 4755.$ $\beta = 40\bar{2}.$

$t^\circ.$	$\eta(o) \times 10^6.$	$\eta(c) \times 10^6.$	% Diff.
0	9435	9409	0.3
10	8832	8830	0.0
20	7432	7432	0.0
30	6689	6689	0.0
40	6067	6056	0.1
50	5527	5518	0.2
60	5065	5053	0.2
70	4662	4654	0.2
80	4304	4306	0.0
90	3987	4002	0.4
100	3714	3732	0.5

isoPropyl iodide.

$\alpha = \bar{4} \cdot 4406,$ $\beta = 411.$

$t^\circ.$	$\eta(o) \times 10^6.$	$\eta(c) \times 10^6.$	% Diff.
0	8841	8832	0.1
10	7814	7814	0.0
20	6971	6972	0.0
30	6268	6272	0.1
40	5676	5672	0.1
50	5162	5166	0.1
60	4731	4730	0.0
70	4347	4350	0.1
80	4005	4027	0.5

Butyl iodide.

$\alpha = \bar{4} \cdot 4414.$ $\beta = 445.$

$t^\circ.$	$\eta(o) \times 10^6.$	$\eta(c) \times 10^6.$	% Diff.
10	10320	10320	0.0
15	9701	9695	0.1
20	9166	9123	0.5
25	8635	8630	0.1
30	8189	8128	0.7
40	7298	7297	0.0
50	6762	6593	2.5(?)

isoButyl iodide.

$\alpha = \bar{4} \cdot 3715.$ $\beta = 461.$

$t^\circ.$	$\eta(o) \times 10^6.$	$\eta(c) \times 10^6.$	% Diff.
0	11660	11490	1.5(?)
10	10010	10010	0.0
20	8753	8808	0.6
30	7774	7815	0.5
40	6970	6987	0.2
50	6291	6290	0.0
60	5712	5701	0.2
70	5218	5194	0.5
80	4785	4763	0.5
90	4397	4381	0.4
100	4064	4049	0.4
110	3770	3760	0.3
120	3496	3504	0.2

Allyl iodide

$$\bar{\alpha} = 4.4537, \quad \beta = 414.$$

t°	$\eta(o) \times 10^6$	$\eta(c) \times 10^6$	% Diff.
0	9358	9337	0.2
10	8255	8252	0.0
20	7338	7355	0.0
30	6596	6617	0.3
40	5972	5975	0.1
50	5440	5437	0.1
60	4987	4977	0.2
70	4585	4578	0.2
80	4237	4231	0.1
90	3936	3927	0.3
100	3652	3661	0.3

All the observed values except those of chlorobenzene, bromobenzene and butyl iodide have been taken directly from the Börnstein-Landolt's table. The values for chloro- and bromobenzenes have been taken from John Castell-Evans Physico-Chemical Tables Vol. II, pages 588-589 and those for butyl iodide have been calculated from the values of relative viscosities given in Börnstein-Landolt's table.

It is evident from the tabulated values of observed and calculated viscosities that agreement between the calculated and observed values is quite good. In very few cases indeed the difference between the two values exceeds 0.5%. All differences greater than 1% can safely be assigned to experimental errors (in case of unassociated liquids only).

The Dependence of α and β on Constitutional Factors.

α and β in the homologous series.—The only regularity which is noted in the $\bar{\alpha}$ values of compounds belonging to a homologous series is that α goes on decreasing as more and more CH_2 groups are added. The difference between the α values of two compounds differing either by a CH_2 or by C_2H_4 group is far from constant. There is no regularity to be observed even if antilog α , i. e., "A" values of Andrade are compared.

β values show some regularity when the values of the two compounds differing by a C_2H_4 group is compared. However, there is no regularity if the values of two compounds differing by CH_2 group are compared. The difference between the β values of *n*-pentane and *n*-heptane is 78, *n*-hexane and *n*-octane 87, methyl iodide and propyl iodide 79, ethyl iodide and butyl iodide 87. These differences may be considered to be approximately constant.

Effect of Replacing Chlorine by Bromine and Bromine by Iodine.

In the following table α , β and A are given for a number of chlorides, bromides and iodides. The difference between α , β and A values of the chlorides and corresponding bromides and that between the bromides and corresponding iodides are indicated by $\Delta\alpha$, $\Delta\beta$ and ΔA

Liquid.	α .	$\Delta\alpha \times 10^4$.	$A \times 10^7$.	$\Delta A \times 10^7$.	β .	$\Delta\beta$.
Chlorobenzene	$\bar{4}$.3278		2227		468	
Bromobenzene	$\bar{4}$.4240	962	2655	428	488	20
Ethyl bromide	4.4601		2885		335	
Ethyl iodide	$\bar{4}$.5501	900	3549	664	358	23
Propyl chloride	$\bar{4}$.3190		2085		362	
Propyl bromide	$\bar{4}$.4216	1026	2640	555	380	18
Propyl iodide	$\bar{4}$.4755	539	2989	349	409	29
<i>iso</i> Propyl chloride	$\bar{4}$.2480		1770		372	
<i>iso</i> Propyl bromide	$\bar{4}$.3582	1102	2281	511	390	18
<i>iso</i> Propyl iodide	$\bar{4}$.4406	824	2758	477	411	21
<i>iso</i> Butyl chloride	$\bar{4}$.2203		1661		423	
<i>iso</i> Butyl bromide	$\bar{4}$.3062	859	2024	363	440	17
<i>iso</i> Butyl iodide	$\bar{4}$.3705	643	2352	328	461	21
Allyl chloride	$\bar{4}$.3299		2137		351	
Allyl bromide	$\bar{4}$.4310	1011	2692	555	373	22
Allyl iodide	$\bar{4}$.4597	227	2842	150	414	41

As is evident from the tabulated values that there is no relationship among the α or A values of chlorides and corresponding bromides

and iodides. The difference between the β values of chlorides and bromides may be considered to be approximately constant. It varies from 17 to 22. The corresponding difference between the bromides and iodides varies from 21 to 41, and so cannot be considered constant even approximately.

SUMMARY.

- (1) The equation $\log \eta = a + \frac{\beta}{T}$ connecting the viscosity of liquids with temperature is derived from the Porter's empirical relation between the vapour pressure and viscosity.
- (2) The viscosity of 25 liquids has been calculated from the above equation and compared with the experimental values.
- (3) No relationship between a and chemical constitution is found.
- (4) The difference between the β values of two compounds belonging to the same homologous series and differing in molecular weight by C_2H_4 is about 80.
- (5) The difference between β values of chlorides and corresponding bromides is about 20.

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